

БОЛАЛАРДА ЖАРРОХЛИК АМАЛИЁТИДАН КЕЙИНГИ АСОРАТЛАНГАН ЧОВ ЧУРРАЛАРИ.

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Муаммонинг долзарблиги: Чурра касалликлари ичида чов чурралари барча чурраларнинг 80% ни ташкил этади. Қийшиқ ва тўғри чов чурралари тафовут қилинади. Қийшиқ чов чурралари туғма, орттирилган, тўғри чов чурраси эса фақат орттирилган бўлади.

Чурра дарвозаси бир биридан ажралиб кетган мушак ва апоневроздан иборат бўлиб, турли шаклга ва айрим ҳолларда жуда катта хажмга эга бўлиши мумкин. Чурралар кўп ҳолларда кўп камерали бўлади. Чурраларнинг умумий сабабларга ирсий омиллар (20-25%), беморнинг ёши (20-40 ёш орасида), жинси (80%- 90% эркаклар касалланади), спланхноптоз (ички аъзоларнинг паст жойлашиши), озиб кетиш, қорин мушакларининг кучсизлиги, қорин бўшлиғи ичидаги босимнинг ошиши сабаб бўлади.

Ишнинг мақсади: ишнинг мақсади сифатида ВКТТМда 2024 йил давомида жаррохлик амалиётидан кейинги асоратланган чов чурралари билан муурожаат қилган беморларнинг анамнестик тахлили, касаллик тарихлари ўрганилди.

Материал ва усуллар: ишнинг материали сифатида ВКТТМда 2024 йил давомида жаррохлик амалиётидан кейинги асоратланган чов чурралари билан муурожаат қилган беморларнинг клиник-лаборатор ва инструментал текширувлар билан текширилди.

Олинган натижалар: 2024 йил давомида ВКТТМнинг жаррохлик бўлимига муурожаат қилиб, жаррохлик бўлимида жаррохлик амалиётидан кейинги асоратланган чов чурралари билан жами 20 нафар беморга қайта жаррохлик амалиётида сеткалардан фойдаланилди ва жароҳат жойига фиксация қилинди.

Хулосалар: хулоса ўрнида шуни айтиш мумкинки, жаррохлик амалиётидан кейинги асоратланган чов чурралар келиб чиқиш сабабли турли хил бўлиб, чурра касаллиги ичида чов чурралари ташхисида клиник-лаборатор ва инструментал текширувлардан ўтказилиби, жаррохлик амалиётларида сеткалардан фойдаланилди.

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